

Supplementary tables from Macroevolutionary lability decouples sexual selection intensity from speciation rate and trait evolution of bony vertebrates

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Table 1: Table S1. PGLS results for each combination of speciation rate as a function of selection index for the full dataset. Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	BAMM	Is	Males	21	-2.837	-0.01	0.0036	0.3302	-0.3782	0.0512	0.4061
All	DR	Is	Males	21	-2.536	0.055	0.0137	0.1617	-0.2173	0.0074	0.2078
All	BAMM	I	Males	62	-2.993	0.034	0.0118	0.1277	-0.2237	0.0153	0.2105
All	DR	I	Males	62	-3.321	0.089	0.0115	0.0445	-0.0824	-0.0098	0.0718
All	BAMM	If	Males	53	-2.989	0.005	0.0003	0.1414	-0.2169	0.0020	0.2131
All	DR	If	Males	53	-3.408	-0.008	0.0001	0.0614	-0.0928	0.0039	0.0927
All	BAMM	Bgm	Males	6	-2.589	0.207	0.0143	0.8128	-0.5698	0.0598	0.6206
All	DR	Bgm	Males	6	-2.685	-0.018	0.0001	0.5428	-0.4710	-0.0172	0.4384
All	BAMM	Bgf	Males	36	-2.917	0.154	0.0389	0.1912	-0.2928	0.0302	0.3044
All	DR	Bgf	Males	36	-3.224	0.113	0.0025	0.0814	-0.1123	0.0056	0.1146
All	BAMM	Is	Females	15	-2.980	0.012	0.0011	0.3414	-0.3458	-0.0042	0.3312
All	DR	Is	Females	15	-3.476	-0.214	0.0868	0.1849	-0.2202	-0.0112	0.2160
All	BAMM	I	Females	55	-2.832	0.008	0.0009	0.1451	-0.2191	-0.0100	0.2247
All	DR	I	Females	55	-3.347	0.03	0.0020	0.0686	-0.0988	0.0073	0.0935
All	BAMM	If	Females	48	-2.785	0.05	0.0121	0.1612	-0.2482	0.0158	0.2459
All	DR	If	Females	48	-3.299	0.012	0.0002	0.0778	-0.1054	0.0244	0.1390
All	BAMM	Bgm	Females	3	—	—	—	16.3177	—	—	—
All	DR	Bgm	Females	3	—	—	—	10.9419	—	—	—
All	BAMM	Bgf	Females	32	-2.893	-0.009	0.0011	0.2304	-0.3266	0.0048	0.3036
All	DR	Bgf	Females	32	-3.485	0.014	0.0003	0.1162	-0.1560	-0.0007	0.1610
Fish	BAMM	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Males	11	-2.381	0.079	0.0640	0.6054	-0.5511	0.0520	0.6067
Fish	DR	I	Males	11	-3.478	-0.073	0.0520	0.2957	-0.3235	0.0114	0.2838
Fish	BAMM	If	Males	11	-2.337	0.044	0.0232	0.6150	-0.5618	-0.0520	0.5637
Fish	DR	If	Males	11	-3.505	-0.065	0.0265	0.2728	-0.2357	0.0169	0.3014
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-2.401	0.007	0.0003	0.6057	-0.5867	0.0639	0.5436
Fish	DR	Bgf	Males	9	-3.648	-0.319	0.1566	0.3573	-0.4282	-0.0180	0.4151
Fish	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Females	10	-2.160	0.053	0.0258	0.7725	-0.6668	-0.0106	0.6779
Fish	DR	I	Females	10	-3.392	0.266	0.2118	0.3602	-0.4760	-0.0501	0.4736
Fish	BAMM	If	Females	10	-1.977	0.132	0.0980	5.7982	-0.6727	-0.0292	0.6956
Fish	DR	If	Females	10	-3.287	0.165	0.0595	0.3918	-0.4163	-0.0269	0.3614
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Females	7	-2.160	-0.004	0.0000	5.4283	-0.6116	-0.0447	0.6826
Fish	DR	Bgf	Females	7	-3.490	0.884*	0.6248	0.7174	-0.8311	0.3012	0.8223
Birds	BAMM	Is	Males	6	-2.668	0.054	0.0615	7.2239	-0.6881	-0.0432	0.6814
Birds	DR	Is	Males	6	-1.550	0.884*†	0.7468	0.4959	-0.8045	-0.0238	0.8081
Birds	BAMM	I	Males	17	-3.089	0.057	0.0431	0.5511	-0.5796	-0.0014	0.6075
Birds	DR	I	Males	17	-3.412	0.365	0.0960	0.1653	-0.2481	0.0090	0.2182

Table 1: Table S1. PGLS results for each combination of speciation ra (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Birds	BAMM	If	Males	15	-3.076	-0.014	0.0051	0.6075	-0.6348	-0.0127	0.6061
Birds	DR	If	Males	15	-3.462	-0.102	0.0117	0.2185	-0.2262	0.0311	0.2544
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-3.008	0.369	0.2395	6.7898	-0.8344	-0.0714	0.7900
Birds	DR	Bgf	Males	9	—	—	—	0.3427	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Is	Females	4	-2.628	0.293	0.2037	8.2440	-0.7793	-0.0511	0.6888
Birds	DR	Is	Females	4	-1.566	0.815	0.4245	4.9944	-0.6788	0.0837	0.6214
Birds	BAMM	I	Females	16	-3.063	0.001	0.0000	0.6009	-0.6230	-0.0040	0.6553
Birds	DR	I	Females	16	-3.357	0.084	0.0243	0.2612	-0.3385	0.0011	0.3129
Birds	BAMM	If	Females	14	-3.047	0.009	0.0004	0.6200	-0.5902	-0.0116	0.5779
Birds	DR	If	Females	14	-2.809	0.298	0.0632	0.3328	-0.3807	-0.0027	0.4020
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Females	10	-3.104	-0.007	0.0019	6.7757	-0.7496	-0.0256	0.6804
Birds	DR	Bgf	Females	10	-2.975	-0.069	0.0259	0.4165	-0.3925	-0.0223	0.4490
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Males	3	-2.389	0.445	0.8827	9.8723	-0.9447	-0.0512	0.9533
Squamates	DR	Is	Males	3	-3.036	0.326	0.3457	11.1928	-0.6680	0.0077	0.6450
Squamates	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.220	0.015	0.0011	6.2964	-0.5757	0.0052	0.6089
Squamates	DR	I	Males	6	-3.123	-0.082	0.0096	0.6195	-0.6005	0.0313	0.5659
Squamates	BAMM	If	Males	6	-3.217	-0.07	0.0709	6.7299	-0.6383	0.0117	0.6197
Squamates	DR	If	Males	6	-3.219	-0.239	0.2114	0.6349	-0.6013	0.0373	0.6330
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	12.0525	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	15.4268	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Females	3	-2.505	0.198	0.3006	11.2164	-0.7344	0.0471	0.7941
Squamates	DR	Is	Females	3	-3.428	-0.005	0.0002	8.9295	-0.5694	0.0032	0.5035
Squamates	BAMM	I	Females	7	-3.192	-0.015	0.0074	6.0460	-0.6310	-0.0226	0.6084
Squamates	DR	I	Females	7	-3.223	-0.092	0.0638	0.5484	-0.5219	-0.0218	0.4708
Squamates	BAMM	If	Females	6	-3.249	-0.039	0.0314	7.1499	-0.6173	0.0402	0.6555
Squamates	DR	If	Females	6	-3.395	-0.201	0.2048	0.6618	-0.5969	-0.0064	0.6896
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	11.2164	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	15.6436	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Males	3	-3.911	1.043*	1.0000	14.6264	-0.9901	0.0548	0.9866
Amphibians	DR	Is	Males	3	-3.343	0.913	0.6210	12.1568	-0.8625	0.0447	0.8065
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Males	8	-3.832	0.142	0.2114	0.6921	-0.7003	-0.0420	0.6698
Amphibians	DR	I	Males	8	-4.332	0.02	0.0024	0.5111	-0.4602	0.0110	0.4498
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Males	6	-3.861	0.035	0.0140	8.3464	-0.6799	0.0008	0.7183
Amphibians	DR	If	Males	6	-4.576	0.043	0.0124	6.2260	-0.6950	-0.0409	0.6922
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Males	5	-3.446	2.071	0.1387	8.8012	-0.7998	0.0115	0.7887
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Males	5	-4.703	-4.85	0.3403	9.0906	-0.8588	0.0278	0.8466
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Females	7	-3.900	-0.306*	0.7222	5.2901	-0.9379	0.1862	0.9389
Amphibians	DR	I	Females	7	-4.589	-0.331	0.3592	0.6086	-0.7144	0.0181	0.7373
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Females	5	-3.776	-0.121	0.2788	9.7710	-0.7552	0.0071	0.8392
Amphibians	DR	If	Females	5	-4.431	-0.129	0.1854	9.1424	-0.7678	0.0712	0.7887
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Females	5	-3.749	-0.095	0.1033	10.2192	-0.7770	-0.0374	0.7981
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Females	5	-4.727	-0.343	0.7565	8.5354	-0.9552	0.1588	0.9409
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Males	9	-1.806	-0.022	0.0646	9.0667	-0.7836	-0.0717	0.7717
Mammals	DR	Is	Males	9	-1.891	0.057	0.0648	0.5639	-0.5362	0.0589	0.5788
Mammals	BAMM	I	Males	20	-2.534	0.002	0.0000	0.2789	-0.3217	0.0138	0.3228
Mammals	DR	I	Males	20	-2.334	0.176	0.0284	0.1184	-0.1462	-0.0010	0.1494
Mammals	BAMM	If	Males	15	-2.524	0.057	0.0111	0.2856	-0.3346	0.0114	0.3725
Mammals	DR	If	Males	15	-2.512	0.487	0.1335	0.1677	-0.2333	-0.0469	0.2076
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Males	10	-2.634	2.089	0.3019	0.5549	-0.6509	0.0750	0.7779
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Males	10	-3.240	1.052	0.0302	0.3415	-0.3179	0.0145	0.3531
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Females	6	-1.942	-0.055	0.0555	10.2196	-0.7565	0.0771	0.7582
Mammals	DR	Is	Females	6	-3.501	-0.462	0.6233	5.4178	-0.8407	-0.1930	0.8547
Mammals	BAMM	I	Females	15	-2.529	0.037	0.0113	0.3000	-0.3376	-0.0083	0.3391
Mammals	DR	I	Females	15	-2.734	0.083	0.0168	0.1700	-0.2013	-0.0079	0.2184
Mammals	BAMM	If	Females	13	-2.363	0.129	0.0529	0.3194	-0.3382	0.0080	0.3568
Mammals	DR	If	Females	13	-2.115	0.448	0.2156	0.1942	-0.3236	-0.0283	0.2839
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Females	7	-2.643	-1.167	0.1013	0.7453	-0.6705	-0.0663	0.6070
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Females	7	-3.665	-5.515	0.5512	0.4179	-0.6445	0.1263	0.6617

Table 2: Table S2. PGLS results for each combination of speciation rate as a function of selection index for the dataset that only includes studies with clear reporting of zero-success individuals. Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	BAMM	Is	Males	16	-2.935	-0.002	0.0003	0.4321	-0.5299	0.0340	0.5056
All	DR	Is	Males	16	-2.718	0.134	0.0598	0.1815	-0.2676	-0.0202	0.2246
All	BAMM	I	Males	42	-2.875	0.029	0.0082	0.1529	-0.2318	0.0057	0.2145
All	DR	I	Males	42	-3.249	0.032	0.0012	0.0515	-0.0566	0.0019	0.0899
All	BAMM	If	Males	34	-2.853	-0.001	0.0000	0.1671	-0.1971	0.0265	0.2357
All	DR	If	Males	34	-3.239	-0.137	0.0113	0.0721	-0.1206	-0.0009	0.1048
All	BAMM	Bgm	Males	4	-2.847	-1.039	0.3380	8.2447	-0.7720	-0.0993	0.7647
All	DR	Bgm	Males	4	-3.283	-1.933	0.3922	1.0861	-0.6102	-0.0371	0.6006
All	BAMM	Bgf	Males	25	-2.834	2.547*†	0.2207	0.2146	-0.3889	0.1437	0.3856
All	DR	Bgf	Males	25	-3.252	0.924	0.0136	0.1068	-0.1343	0.0279	0.1341
All	BAMM	Is	Females	5	-2.346	0.017	0.0020	5.8186	-0.6583	0.0233	0.6102
All	DR	Is	Females	5	-3.502	-0.23	0.2641	0.6044	-0.6046	0.0053	0.6054
All	BAMM	I	Females	25	-2.743	-0.03	0.0030	0.1995	-0.2342	0.0222	0.2466
All	DR	I	Females	25	-3.090	-0.002	0.0000	0.0973	-0.1476	0.0134	0.1286
All	BAMM	If	Females	23	-2.754	0.025	0.0013	0.1933	-0.2621	0.0084	0.2400
All	DR	If	Females	23	-3.135	0.062	0.0038	0.1108	-0.1417	-0.0153	0.1293
All	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	BAMM	Bgf	Females	18	-2.905	0.139	0.0105	0.2684	-0.2903	-0.0028	0.3297
All	DR	Bgf	Females	18	-3.563	0.049	0.0008	0.1626	-0.1785	-0.0436	0.1693
Birds	BAMM	Is	Males	4	-2.790	0.109	0.2769	13.1408	-0.8837	-0.0026	0.8888
Birds	DR	Is	Males	4	-1.768	0.525*†	0.9940	4.7379	-0.9862	-0.3352	0.9810
Birds	BAMM	I	Males	9	—	—	—	0.7479	—	—	—
Birds	DR	I	Males	9	—	—	—	0.1869	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	If	Males	7	—	—	—	6.8433	—	—	—
Birds	DR	If	Males	7	—	—	—	0.2694	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Males	4	-2.838	-0.708	0.0167	10.9030	-0.7494	0.0622	0.7526
Birds	DR	Bgf	Males	4	-0.562	14.418	0.2853	0.6108	-0.4675	0.0187	0.4182
Birds	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	I	Females	6	-2.700	0.026	0.0160	10.2312	-0.7821	-0.0584	0.7236
Birds	DR	I	Females	6	-1.979	0.385	0.3601	0.5457	-0.5933	0.1548	0.6651
Birds	BAMM	If	Females	5	-2.534	0.127	0.0872	10.2329	-0.7557	-0.0686	0.7515
Birds	DR	If	Females	5	-1.018	0.914	0.4025	0.6259	-0.6595	0.0495	0.6638
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Females	4	-2.768	0.013	0.0009	12.9924	-0.7718	0.0556	0.8099
Birds	DR	Bgf	Females	4	-2.334	0.587	0.1623	5.8247	-0.5089	-0.0316	0.5764
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	I	Males	5	-3.612	0.301	0.5928	8.8201	-0.8949	0.1384	0.8974
Squamates	DR	I	Males	5	-3.761	0.19	0.1653	8.6523	-0.7146	-0.0361	0.6674
Squamates	BAMM	If	Males	5	-3.419	0.213	0.4876	9.9616	-0.8870	0.1062	0.8674
Squamates	DR	If	Males	5	-3.662	0.199	0.2309	8.2022	-0.7736	0.0574	0.7774
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	12.1701	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	16.3564	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	I	Females	4	-3.255	0.003	0.0001	10.5977	-0.7743	0.0494	0.7350
Squamates	DR	I	Females	4	-3.329	-0.202	0.4272	9.9653	-0.7874	-0.0928	0.8551
Squamates	BAMM	If	Females	4	-3.262	0.04	0.0115	9.2028	-0.7345	0.0066	0.7059
Squamates	DR	If	Females	4	-3.325	-0.189	0.3475	9.3922	-0.7736	0.1442	0.8060
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	13.3471	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	14.8565	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.815	0.125	0.2840	6.1164	-0.7448	-0.0991	0.7827
Amphibians	DR	I	Males	6	-4.236	-0.014	0.0028	0.6323	-0.4821	-0.0390	0.4455
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Males	4	-3.569	-0.146	0.1390	9.5132	-0.7876	0.0109	0.8045
Amphibians	DR	If	Males	4	-4.728	0.176	0.1880	10.3538	-0.7479	0.0860	0.7991
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 2: Table S2. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Males	4	-3.477	3.39	0.3385	10.8387	-0.7995	0.0418	0.8819
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Males	4	-4.773	-2.59	0.1337	11.7848	-0.7946	-0.0408	0.8190
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Females	5	-3.824	-0.334*	0.8150	6.8801	-0.9344	-0.0595	0.9251
Amphibians	DR	I	Females	5	-4.667	-0.375	0.5193	0.6481	-0.7273	0.1038	0.7121
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Females	4	-3.811	-0.11	0.2409	10.9086	-0.8270	0.0609	0.8212
Amphibians	DR	If	Females	4	-4.653	-0.034	0.0160	10.7098	-0.8221	0.0030	0.8151
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Females	4	-3.740	-0.073	0.0097	12.8154	-0.7801	-0.0550	0.7668
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Females	4	-4.827	-0.637	0.7281	14.0792	-0.9508	-0.1086	0.9226
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Males	8	-1.851	-0.018	0.0432	8.5216	-0.7866	0.0476	0.8223
Mammals	DR	Is	Males	8	-1.803	0.05	0.0472	0.5758	-0.5390	-0.0258	0.5143
Mammals	BAMM	I	Males	16	-2.436	-0.021	0.0051	0.3301	-0.3537	-0.0501	0.3664
Mammals	DR	I	Males	16	-2.291	0.09	0.0068	0.1362	-0.1514	-0.0174	0.1618
Mammals	BAMM	If	Males	12	-2.406	-0.019	0.0012	0.3378	-0.3600	-0.0399	0.2837
Mammals	DR	If	Males	12	-2.404	0.642	0.1114	0.2029	-0.2197	-0.0290	0.2389
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-2.651	2.19	0.3229	0.5780	-0.7203	-0.0260	0.7057
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Males	9	-3.495	1.889	0.1604	0.4859	-0.5352	-0.0115	0.5675
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	I	Females	8	-2.490	0.119	0.0818	0.5298	-0.5438	-0.0301	0.5050
Mammals	DR	I	Females	8	-3.475	0.495	0.3698	0.3022	-0.4456	0.0633	0.4426
Mammals	BAMM	If	Females	8	-2.163	-0.141	0.0316	0.4962	-0.4262	0.0151	0.4812
Mammals	DR	If	Females	8	-2.957	0.137	0.0129	0.3587	-0.2947	0.0165	0.3126
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Females	5	-2.979	-0.04	0.0001	9.3278	-0.6715	0.0171	0.6858
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Females	5	-4.037	0.318	0.0016	5.0396	-0.5795	-0.0229	0.5680
Fish	BAMM	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.011	0.666*	0.6980	0.7006	-0.8379	-0.1322	0.8920
Fish	DR	I	Males	6	-3.640	-0.146	0.0750	5.7105	-0.6609	-0.0236	0.6760
Fish	BAMM	If	Males	6	-2.542	0.768	0.5792	0.6722	-0.8282	0.1125	0.8078
Fish	DR	If	Males	6	-3.747	-0.186	0.0763	6.1418	-0.6986	0.0493	0.7044
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Males	5	—	—	—	0.7972	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgf	Males	5	-3.722	-1.044	0.0819	6.6959	-0.7196	0.0289	0.6147
Fish	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 3: Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of trait as a function of selection index (full dataset). Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	6	0.141	0.03	0.0514	11.5359	-0.8386	-0.0734	0.8435
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	16	-0.461	-0.142*	0.2571	0.1373	-0.2614	-0.0738	0.2694
All	SSD (length)	I	Males	9	0.044	-0.014	0.0802	12.5167	-0.8709	0.0211	0.8650
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	14	0.078	-0.142*†	0.3317	8.9161	-0.9415	-0.1054	0.9441
All	SSD (weight)	I	Males	41	-0.235	-0.104	0.0905	0.1915	-0.3462	0.0071	0.3734
All	SSD (length)	If	Males	9	0.041	-0.011	0.0392	11.2073	-0.8743	-0.0021	0.8750
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	12	0.013	-0.01	0.0264	10.2512	-0.8813	0.0575	0.8825
All	SSD (weight)	If	Males	34	-0.178	-0.037	0.0330	0.3193	-0.4610	0.0104	0.4826

Table 3: Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of tra (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Trait	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	5	-0.309	0.044	0.0098	10.0368	-0.7339	0.0349	0.7733
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	6	0.057	-0.03	0.0597	14.6627	-0.8957	0.0350	0.9060
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	8	0.016	-0.016	0.0001	15.5371	-0.9117	0.0166	0.8790
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	22	-0.134	0.04	0.0051	0.4588	-0.5649	-0.0254	0.5534
All	SSD (length)	Is	Females	3	-0.239	-0.064	0.6439	13.6634	-0.9097	0.0120	0.9473
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	4	0.035	-0.026	0.3926	13.9362	-0.9143	-0.0746	0.9430
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	11	-0.441	-0.079	0.0132	0.2997	-0.3898	-0.0081	0.2827
All	SSD (length)	I	Females	8	0.006	0.004	0.0029	9.9099	-0.8066	-0.0701	0.8022
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	14	0.013	-0.021	0.1159	10.1796	-0.8962	-0.0027	0.8897
All	SSD (weight)	I	Females	35	-0.221	-0.049*†	0.1267	0.3164	-0.4777	-0.0370	0.4974
All	SSD (length)	If	Females	6	0.021	0.017	0.1319	12.9255	-0.9010	-0.0622	0.8709
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	11	-0.012	-0.01	0.0306	11.5163	-0.8754	-0.0524	0.8604
All	SSD (weight)	If	Females	32	-0.305	-0.047*†	0.1672	0.4023	-0.6644	-0.0965	0.6547
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	3	-0.022	0.128	0.8206	15.2506	-0.9416	-0.0786	0.9329
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	8	0.008	-0.011	0.0121	13.9453	-0.8987	-0.0159	0.9137
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	20	-0.198	-0.014	0.0170	0.6162	-0.6691	-0.0224	0.6471
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	—	—	—	—	12.5961	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Males	17	-0.168	-0.107*	0.3467	6.6475	-0.9237	0.0423	0.9216
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Males	15	-0.248	-0.082	0.2474	6.7571	-0.8838	0.0269	0.9017
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	9	-0.014	-0.035	0.0248	13.0333	-0.9072	-0.0023	0.8983
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	4	0.665	0.168	0.5903	12.8065	-0.9527	-0.0197	0.9340
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Females	16	-0.341	-0.046	0.1793	6.8326	-0.8681	-0.0164	0.8918
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Females	14	-0.511	-0.101	0.2314	8.6319	-0.8868	0.0713	0.9202
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	10.8492	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	3	0.001	0.002	0.0040	16.4319	-0.9387	0.1080	0.9314
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	6	-0.060	0.034	0.1011	12.6333	-0.8997	0.0186	0.8759
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Males	4	-0.119	0.084	0.0561	11.2626	-0.7508	0.0116	0.7228
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	6	-0.029	0.015	0.0501	17.7299	-0.9128	-0.0226	0.8913
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	9.4202	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	14.5431	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	12.3005	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	3	-0.031	-0.014	0.2981	11.8724	-0.9568	0.0936	0.9771
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	7	-0.022	-0.006	0.0168	11.9723	-0.8810	0.0872	0.8855
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Females	4	-0.066	-0.081	0.4669	10.2912	-0.8541	0.1738	0.8788
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	6	-0.037	-0.009	0.0248	12.7857	-0.8830	-0.0219	0.8618
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Females	4	-0.062	-0.115	0.4519	11.7883	-0.8754	-0.0143	0.8477
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 3: Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of tra (*continued*)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	16.7960	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	14.5436	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	3	0.306	-0.174	0.3085	13.5588	-0.8935	-0.0993	0.8785
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	8	0.125	-0.073*†	0.6145	11.0389	-0.9805	-0.0119	0.9823
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	6	0.043	-0.033	0.6103	15.2402	-0.9063	-0.1573	0.9954
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	5	0.038	0.075	0.0074	13.5619	-0.9323	0.0219	0.9402
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	7	-0.004	-0.107*†	0.7595	13.8639	-0.9337	0.6786	0.9909
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	5	0.026	-0.005	0.0161	15.5882	-0.9004	0.0428	0.9400
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	5	0.008	-0.015	0.1391	16.8277	-0.9726	0.0253	0.9478
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	9	-0.668	-0.105	0.1095	0.2877	-0.2588	0.0111	0.3150
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.011	0.004	0.0538	15.1620	-0.9216	-0.0011	0.9194
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Males	18	-0.375	-0.142	0.1020	0.3258	-0.4641	-0.0234	0.4148
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.010	0.007	0.1047	15.5432	-0.9411	0.0341	0.9390
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Males	13	-0.435	0	0.0000	0.6322	-0.6059	-0.0016	0.6008
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	10	-0.311	0.716	0.2556	6.5652	-0.8454	0.0091	0.7906
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Females	3	-0.239	-0.064	0.6439	14.7580	-0.9154	0.0390	0.9359
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	6	-1.057	-0.228	0.1601	0.6511	-0.5894	-0.0428	0.6362
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Females	4	-0.016	0.015	0.0957	15.1286	-0.9428	-0.0131	0.9113
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Females	13	-0.513	-0.029	0.0372	0.5337	-0.5525	0.0019	0.5287
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Females	12	-0.624	-0.062	0.1480	5.6413	-0.7558	-0.0540	0.7720
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	7	-0.482	-0.25	0.0646	11.6480	-0.8532	0.0701	0.8886
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Males	—	—	—	—	15.3316	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Males	5	0.066	-0.005	0.0027	15.8074	-0.9236	-0.0643	0.9283
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 3: Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of tra (*continued*)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	4	0.090	-0.047	0.2558	12.7557	-0.9558	0.0943	0.9674
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Females	4	-0.008	-0.053	0.2920	16.7617	-0.9443	-0.1169	0.9365
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Females	4	0.081	0.021	0.1651	15.1422	-0.9452	0.0133	0.9164
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Males	3	-2.026	-0.57	0.4106	11.9908	-0.8143	0.0076	0.8234
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Males	3	-2.955	-0.892	0.7234	12.6746	-0.9359	-0.0650	0.9043
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Males	3	-1.701	-0.419	0.3704	14.7231	-0.8741	0.0667	0.8751
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Males	11	0.516	-0.127	0.0198	0.1935	-0.2142	-0.0006	0.1629
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Males	11	0.278	0.056	0.0108	0.3847	-0.3957	0.0037	0.4044
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Males	11	0.309	-0.199	0.0746	0.3010	-0.2924	-0.0379	0.3098
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Males	9	0.727	0.029	0.0013	0.1929	-0.2135	-0.0006	0.1761
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Males	9	0.645	0.241	0.2350	0.4261	-0.5430	0.0662	0.5535
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Males	9	0.592	0.091	0.0190	0.3125	-0.3123	-0.0194	0.3024
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Males	4	0.682	0.049	0.0010	6.4541	-0.4873	-0.0022	0.5303
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Males	4	0.338	0.048	0.0018	9.0851	-0.6527	-0.0508	0.6326
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Males	4	0.685	-0.439	0.0694	6.9739	-0.6269	-0.0091	0.5465
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Females	3	-1.815	-0.518	0.8313	15.8206	-0.9383	0.0699	0.9372
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Females	3	-2.211	-0.666	0.9897	12.0101	-0.9838	-0.0798	0.9910
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Females	3	-1.582	-0.393	0.7993	16.1932	-0.9262	-0.0810	0.9548
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Females	10	0.810	0.178	0.0517	0.2043	-0.1876	0.0183	0.2307
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Females	10	0.315	0.008	0.0003	0.3924	-0.4189	0.0068	0.3439
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Females	10	0.260	-0.055	0.0078	0.2892	-0.3273	-0.0407	0.2893
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Females	8	0.765	0.251	0.0418	0.3740	-0.2912	0.0215	0.3066
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Females	8	0.218	-0.009	0.0001	0.4524	-0.3729	-0.0208	0.4031
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Females	8	0.545	0.111	0.0069	0.3669	-0.3359	0.0011	0.3073
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.989	-0.508	0.7598	0.8605	-0.9014	-0.1257	0.8682
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	8.5268	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.803	-0.534	0.6919	0.7525	-0.8031	0.1116	0.8439

Table 4: Table S4. PGLS results for each combination of trait as a function of selection index (including only studies that clearly reported zero-success individuals - "zero-only dataset"). Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	4	0.153	-0.005	0.0035	12.3160	-0.8777	0.0483	0.8579
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	13	-0.492	-0.127	0.1683	0.1360	-0.2093	0.0316	0.2090
All	SSD (length)	I	Males	8	0.039	-0.007	0.0114	14.2880	-0.8900	0.0340	0.8603
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	11	0.094	-0.052*	0.3626	8.8195	-0.9404	0.0244	0.9454
All	SSD (weight)	I	Males	28	-0.272	-0.108	0.0723	0.2065	-0.3066	-0.0037	0.3556
All	SSD (length)	If	Males	8	0.037	-0.003	0.0016	13.5814	-0.8722	-0.0062	0.8666
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	9	-0.003	0.005	0.0028	10.8551	-0.8531	0.0238	0.8306
All	SSD (weight)	If	Males	22	-0.209	-0.022	0.0067	0.4448	-0.5008	0.0158	0.5214
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 4: Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Trait	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	3	-0.451	0.873	0.6530	15.5371	-0.8886	0.0361	0.9242
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	5	0.056	-0.046	0.0129	14.4141	-0.9017	-0.0332	0.8863
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	7	0.016	0.12	0.0042	11.2783	-0.8563	-0.0657	0.9017
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	16	-0.164	0.597	0.1566	0.6666	-0.7543	-0.0686	0.7548
All	SSD (length)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	—	—	—	—	15.7472	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	I	Females	3	0.013	0.006	0.9630	12.6437	-0.9342	-0.0093	0.9190
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	9	0.006	-0.062*	0.4803	9.8660	-0.9739	0.2187	0.9636
All	SSD (weight)	I	Females	16	-0.236	-0.052*†	0.3558	0.6206	-0.8311	-0.2101	0.8330
All	SSD (length)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	8	-0.009	-0.023	0.1097	12.8698	-0.8589	0.0321	0.8992
All	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	0.6120	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	7	0.014	0.007	0.0005	13.6755	-0.8499	-0.0642	0.9132
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	12	-0.241	-0.105	0.0522	5.8680	-0.7008	-0.0010	0.6852
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	5	-0.058	0.033	0.0874	14.3976	-0.9187	0.0514	0.8636
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Males	4	-0.119	0.084	0.0561	10.2808	-0.7961	-0.0118	0.7054
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	5	-0.033	0.019	0.0376	13.1315	-0.8974	-0.0372	0.8982
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	10.7702	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	13.9908	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	12.6973	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	4	-0.015	-0.044	0.2108	15.4115	-0.9185	0.1929	0.9354
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	13.9048	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	4	-0.015	-0.036	0.1298	14.9350	-0.9133	0.0506	0.8908
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	14.3075	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	14.4422	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	12.7857	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	6	0.143	-0.058	0.6562	12.2051	-0.9740	0.3166	0.9702
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	4	0.016	-0.013	0.0845	17.2918	-0.9390	0.0715	0.9283
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	4	0.017	0.181	0.0800	15.5467	-0.9316	-0.0743	0.9371
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	5	-0.006	-0.068	0.7356	13.9250	-0.9794	-0.1875	0.9718
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	4	0.009	0.005	0.0342	12.9577	-0.9155	0.0607	0.9400
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 4: Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	4	0.028	0.044	0.2954	13.7745	-0.9621	-0.0845	0.9415
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	8	-0.779	-0.065	0.0365	0.2906	-0.2473	-0.0070	0.2149
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.012	0.003	0.0232	17.1587	-0.8923	-0.0280	0.9302
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Males	14	-0.426	-0.113	0.0548	0.3690	-0.4528	-0.0194	0.4358
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.010	0.007	0.1047	14.8044	-0.9322	0.0521	0.9656
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Males	10	-0.531	0.073	0.2092	8.4434	-0.8377	-0.0176	0.8302
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	9	-0.376	0.729	0.3430	9.9087	-0.9183	0.0239	0.9238
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Females	7	-0.402	-0.088	0.4822	10.6679	-0.9109	0.1140	0.9191
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Females	7	-0.347	-0.127	0.5545	10.2504	-0.9688	-0.1960	0.9465
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.461	0.225	0.0165	12.5224	-0.8460	0.0417	0.8638
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.060	-0.013	0.0143	15.9413	-0.9404	-0.0875	0.9354
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.072	0.019	0.0177	18.3807	-0.8981	0.0730	0.9241
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	3	0.116	0.105	0.0694	15.8103	-0.9477	-0.0274	0.9405
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	4	-0.149	-0.018	0.1275	16.4027	-0.9175	0.0684	0.9126
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Males	9	-0.330	-0.094*	0.4792	10.8696	-0.9628	-0.1868	0.9483
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	10.1280	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 4: Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (*continued*)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	4	-0.157	-0.353	0.0567	13.7158	-0.9205	0.0105	0.9143
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Females	6	-0.226	-0.047	0.3332	12.7333	-0.9450	0.0606	0.9204
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	12.7550	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	4	-0.133	-0.023	0.0284	14.0889	-0.9450	0.0103	0.9021
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Males	6	0.248	0.14	0.1246	0.4817	-0.5445	-0.0399	0.4958
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Males	6	0.180	0.339	0.5374	0.6121	-0.7383	-0.0436	0.6941
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Males	6	0.019	0.181	0.4516	0.7801	-0.7875	-0.1817	0.7964
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Males	4	0.409	-0.025	0.0069	4.5498	-0.4351	-0.0312	0.4582
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Males	4	0.327	0.331	0.6213	5.1029	-0.6490	0.1042	0.7599
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Males	4	0.112	0.142	0.3390	6.4243	-0.7272	0.0744	0.6949
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	12.3305	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	12.1441	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	14.6567	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table 5: Table S5. "Background" phylogenetic signal and continuous character evolution results of sexual selection intensity, some traits that are used in the literature as proxies for sexual selection, and body size for all vertebrates, separated by sex when appropriate. Estimates in bold (and also with an asterisk) refer to significant phylogenetic signal (i.e., close from $\lambda = 1$, or different from random permutations of the data in the phylogeny, in the case of Blomberg's K, Abouheif's C, and Moran's I). All data were log-transformed at base 2 before analysis. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichr - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Index	Sex	Best Model	Phylo Signal	Estimate	Sample size
Bgf	Females	WN	Blomberg's K	0.06585	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Pagel's lambda	0.06646	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Moran's I	-0.07436	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.05325	32
Bgf	Males	OU	Blomberg's K	0.10096	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.15496	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Moran's I	0.28816*	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Abouheif's C	0.29832*	36
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Blomberg's K	1.02739	3
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Pagel's lambda	5e-05	3

Table 5: Table S5. "Background" phylogenetic signal and continuous character evolution results of sexual selection intensity, some traits that are used in the literature as proxies for sexual selection, and body size for all vertebrates, separated by sex when appropriate. Estimates in bold (and also with an asterisk) refer to significant phylogenetic signal (i.e., close from $\lambda = 1$, or different from random permutations of the data in the phylogeny, in the case of Blomberg's K, Abouheif's C, and Moran's I). All data were log-transformed at base 2 before analysis. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index (*continued*)

Index	Sex	Best Model	Phylo Signal	Estimate	Sample size
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Moran's I	-0.44694	3
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Abouheif's C	0.07959	3
Bgm	Males	WN	Blomberg's K	0.17252	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Pagel's lambda	7e-05	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Moran's I	-0.47826	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.24665	6
I	Females	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.09481	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.01115	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.02577	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.0412	55
I	Males	OU	Blomberg's K	0.10721*	62
I	Males	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.74129	62
I	Males	OU	Moran's I	0.24496*	62
I	Males	OU	Abouheif's C	0.2588*	62
If	Females	OU	Blomberg's K	0.20886*	48
If	Females	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.24203	48
If	Females	OU	Moran's I	0.08263	48
If	Females	OU	Abouheif's C	0.10662	48
If	Males	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.09102	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.21714	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.13976	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.15811	53
Is	Females	WN	Blomberg's K	0.13755	15
Is	Females	WN	Pagel's lambda	7e-05	15
Is	Females	WN	Moran's I	-0.14237	15
Is	Females	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.06595	15
Is	Males	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.11154	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.09555	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.19825	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.22608	21
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Blomberg's K	0.04372	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Pagel's Lambda	0.90765*	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Moran's I	0.33312*	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Abouheif's C	0.34241*	53
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.48203	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	0.20092	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Moran's I	0.10995	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	0.14751	17
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.10272	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Pagel's Lambda	0.18908	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.00203	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.10478	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Blomberg's K	0.50311	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Moran's I	-0.07374	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Abouheif's C	0.03922	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.38389	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Moran's I	-0.2309	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.15946	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.21853	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Moran's I	-0.10125	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.06351	12
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Blomberg's K	0.694958263895248*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Pagel's Lambda	1.00164128866343*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Moran's I	0.651426488813106*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Abouheif's C	0.678858376979092*	53

Table 6: Table S6. Summary of significant analyses, per the p-value of the slope (Hypothesis tested: significantly different from zero). Legend: Bgf = Fertilization-based Bateman gradient; Bgm = Mating-based Bateman gradient; I = Mating success index; If = fertilization success index; I = Reproductive success index.

Clade	Sex	Independent variable	Predicted variable	Dataset	Sample size	Effect
Fish	Females	Bgf	DR	full	7	Positive

Table 6: Table S6. Summary of significant analyses, per the p-value of the slope (Hypothesis tested: significantly different from zero). Legend: Bgf = Fertilization-based Bateman gradient; Bgm = Mating-based Bateman gradient; I = Mating success index; If = fertilization success index; I = Reproducti (*continued*)

Clade	Sex	Independent variable	Predicted variable	Dataset	Sample size	Effect
Birds	Males	Is	DR	full	6	Positive
Amphibians	Males	Is	BAMM	full	3	Positive
Amphibians	Females	I	BAMM	full	7	Negative
All	Males	Bgf	BAMM	zero-only	25	Positive
Birds	Males	Is	DR	zero-only	4	Negative
Amphibians	Females	I	BAMM	zero-only	5	Negative
Fish	Males	I	BAMM	zero-only	6	Positive
All	Males	Is	SSD (weight)	full	16	Negative
All	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	full	14	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (weight)	full	35	Negative
All	Females	If	SSD (weight)	full	32	Negative
Birds	Males	I	SSD (weight)	full	17	Negative
Amphibians	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	full	8	Negative
Amphibians	Females	I	SSD (SVL)	full	7	Negative
All	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	zero-only	11	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (SVL)	zero-only	9	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (weight)	zero-only	16	Negative
Birds	Males	I	SSD (weight)	zero-only	9	Negative

Table 7: Table S7. Deviance tables of log2 DR speciation rates explained by different taxonomic groups.

Factor	DF	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	P value
Clade	4	6877.0	1719.26	4209.2207	< 2.2e-16
Tax. Family	947	16456.9	17.38	42.5460	< 2.2e-16
Genus	6074	13448.0	2.21	5.4205	< 2.2e-16
Residual	21058	8601.1	0.41	—	

Table 8: Table S8. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).

Dataset	Speciation rate estimate	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Full dataset	DR	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	DR	Birds	Females	4
Full dataset	DR	Birds	Males	3
Full dataset	DR	Fish	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Fish	Males	3
Full dataset	DR	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	DR	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	DR	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Squamates	Males	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Birds	Females	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Birds	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Fish	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Fish	Males	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Squamates	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Birds	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Birds	Males	2
Zero-only	DR	Fish	Females	0
Zero-only	DR	Fish	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Mammals	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only	DR	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only	DR	Squamates	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Birds	Females	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Birds	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Fish	Females	0
Zero-only	BAMM	Fish	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Mammals	Females	3

Table 8: Table S8. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).
(continued)

Dataset	Speciation rate estimate	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Zero-only	BAMM	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only	BAMM	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Squamates	Males	2

Table 9: Table S9. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).

Dataset	Operationalization of SSD	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Full dataset	Length	Fish	Females	2
Full dataset	Length	Fish	Males	2
Full dataset	Length	Mammals	Females	2
Full dataset	Length	Mammals	Males	2
Full dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	SVL	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	SVL	Squamates	Males	3
Full dataset	Weight	Birds	Females	3
Full dataset	Weight	Birds	Males	3
Full dataset	Weight	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	Weight	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	Weight	Squamates	Females	2
Full dataset	Weight	Squamates	Males	1
Zero-only dataset	Length	Fish	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	Length	Mammals	Males	2
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Squamates	Males	2
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Birds	Females	2
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Birds	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Mammals	Females	3
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Squamates	Males	1